

**CRACK DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT: A CANDIDATE
FRACTURE TOUGHNESS PARAMETER
FOR SHORT FIBER COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

In brittle matrix composites, crack propagation occurs along random trajectories reflecting the heterogeneous nature of the strength field. Considering the crack trajectory as a diffusive process, the "crack diffusion coefficient" is introduced. From fatigue crack propagation experiments on a set of identical SEN polyester composite specimens, the variance of the crack tip position along the loading axis $\sigma^2(y)$ is found to be a linear function of the effective "time". The latter, with the dimension of length, is taken as $\lambda = EG_1/\pi\sigma_\infty^2$, where E is Young's modulus, G_1 is the energy release rate and σ_∞ is the remotely applied stress. The coefficient of proportionality between $\sigma^2(y)$ and λ defines the crack diffusion coefficient D which is found in the present study to be 0.165 mm. This parameter reflects the ability of the composite to deviate the crack from the energetically most efficient path and thus links fracture toughness to the microstructure.

INTRODUCTION

Recognizing the importance of microdefects in fracture, two extreme cases are distinguished. The first is coined as "cooperative fracture", and the second as "single-path fracture". Cooperative fracture involves damage growth as a response to the stress concentration in a region

adjacent to the crack tip. The intensity of the newly formed damage (defects) is significantly larger than that of the pre-existing damage. In this case, crack propagation is inseparable from damage growth. The system of the crack and the accompanying damage is referred to as a crack layer (CL). The CL theory [1, 2] identifies the crack driving forces as integral characteristics of the damage zone. The theory has been verified experimentally for different materials including short fiber composites [3-6].

Single-path fracture, on the other hand, characterizes the case in which the intensity of pre-existing defects (damage) is significantly greater than the newly formed damage. Thus, the field of pre-existing defects controls crack growth. Fluctuations in the defect field lead to scatter in the critical crack length, the crack trajectory and in the critical stress. The critical energy release rate is subsequently scattered and can not be directly considered as a material parameter characteristic of its toughness. Whereas cooperative fracture may involve brittle or ductile mechanisms of damage formation, single path fracture is always brittle. This paper examines single-path fracture in brittle polyester matrix composite and introduces the concept of crack diffusion; a potentially useful approach to characterize the fracture toughness of such materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Single edge notched specimens were prepared from twelve inch compression molded plaques of Premi-Glas, 1.5 mm thick. Premi-Glas is a polyester reinforced with 9% 1/8 inch chopped Kevlar 29 fibers and 14% inorganic glass bead filler. The specimens were machined to a width of 25 mm and length of 150 mm. A sixty degree V-notch of 1.5 mm deep is machined at the center edge of the specimen to initiate crack propagation.

Fatigue crack propagation tests were conducted at room temperature in air using a MTS testing system equipped with a 1 kip load cell. Sinusoidal loading was used with a load ratio, minimum to maximum, of 0.02 and a frequency of 0.5 Hz. The specimen was mounted with 100 mm between the grips. A maximum stress of 15 MNm^{-2} which is 33% of the ultimate failure strength was used in order to obtain measurable crack propagation within reasonable testing times. Fatigue crack propagation was monitored through the use of a traveling optical microscope attached to a video recording system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crack trajectories in the composite studied are observed to deviate from the usual rectilinear path, perpendicular to the direction of the applied load, by as much as thirty degrees in either direction. Figure 1

Figure 1: Three fatigue failed SEN specimens of Premi-Glas composite showing extreme crack trajectories.

shows three identical fatigue failed samples with the extremes of the trajectories. That is, one sample's crack propagated at approximately thirty degrees in the positive direction, i.e., above the plane normal to the applied stress. The middle trajectory propagated along a generally rectilinear path and in the third sample along a path 30 degrees in the negative direction. Each trajectory is unique to a given sample. No two trajectories are ever identical because of the random nature of the strength field. Although the samples are macroscopically identical, the microscopic nature of each sample is unique. A propagating crack assumingly follows the weakest path through the material.

Fracture toughness is a measure of the material resistance to crack propagation. For a random crack path as that shown in Fig. 1, fracture toughness is a functional of the crack trajectory. Thus, fracture toughness becomes a random variable which can be characterized by its moments such as mathematical expectation, variance, etc. As the material becomes more homogeneous, the scatter in fracture toughness would decrease, i.e., the variance tends to vanish and the mean value (mathematical expectation) becomes the only fracture toughness parameter.

Distribution of crack trajectories

In Fig. 2, trajectories from a set of twenty five (identically prepared and loaded) specimens have been superimposed upon the same set of coordinate axes. The propagating crack possesses a deterministic forward movement due to the stress field being applied as well as a lateral movement due to fluctuations of the strength field. The combined effect of both movements results in diffusion type trajectories. We note that the specimen geometry is symmetrical around the x axis as is the applied load. This set was statistically satisfactory and was subsequently used for diffusion analysis.

Figure 2: Crack trajectories of 25 identical specimens. Solid points indicate the onset of critical crack propagation.

The critical crack lengths observed from the video tapes of the fracture process are marked on Fig. 2. The actual values of l_c varied between 6.3 and 13.0 mm. The angle of crack trajectory with respect to the horizontal axis varied between -30 and $+30$ degrees and closely followed a normal distribution [7]. As can be seen from Fig. 2, the critical crack length shows no correlation to the angle of propagation. The variation of the fracture stress for the samples tested was also approximated by normal distribution.

Energy Release Rate

Since the crack trajectories are skewed, energy release rate G_1 calculations accounted for mixed mode crack propagation behavior (modes I and II). Accordingly, G_1 is given by [7]

$$G_1 = \frac{\sigma_\infty^2 \pi \ell [\text{Cos}^4 \theta f_{\text{I}}^2(a/b) + \text{Cos}^2 \theta \text{Sin}^2 \theta f_{\text{II}}^2(a/b)]}{E} \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

where σ_∞ is the remotely applied stress, ℓ is the crack length, a is its projection on the normal to the applied stress, and θ is the average angle of the trajectory, $f_{\text{I}}(a/b)$ and $f_{\text{II}}(a/b)$ are geometric functions, and E is Young's modulus.

In crack propagation, the transition from stable, slow crack growth to uncontrolled, avalanche-like propagation is readily observed. Depending on loading history, this transition occurs at a certain combination of stress and crack length. These are traditionally identified as the critical stress σ_c and critical crack length ℓ_c . The (critical) energy release rate G_{1c} associated with transition is obviously expressed in terms of σ_c and ℓ_c in equation (1).

Figure 3 shows histogram of the critical energy release rate G_{1c} computed from equation (1). The solid line presents the theoretical distribution [7]. The values of G_{1c} vary between 1 and 12 kJ/m^2 , although the test specimens were identically prepared and tested.

Figure 3: Histogram of the critical energy release rate.

The average $\langle G_{1c} \rangle$ is 6.9 kJ/m^2 and the standard deviation is 3.9 kJ/m^2 . Limitation of the usefulness of G_{1c} in the characterization of the fracture toughness of such a material is obvious. This is particularly true when a material toughness parameter is sought to be related to its

microstructure.

Crack Diffusion Coefficient

The enhanced fracture toughness of reinforced composites results from their ability to deviate the crack from its most efficient path, i.e., from the maximum energy release rate trajectory. Thus, the "diffusion" of crack trajectories can be taken as a characteristic of toughness. An approach to quantify this idea is outlined below.

The set of crack trajectories (Fig. 2) resembles one dimensional Brownian motion. The widening of the set with crack length can be quantitatively characterized by the evolution of the probability distribution of the crack trajectory intersection with vertical lines positioned at various distances from the notch tip. Figure 4 shows the

Figure 4: Evolution of probability distribution of the intersects of crack trajectory with vertical lines positioned at various distances from notch tip.

progression of such probability distribution. Near the notch tip, the distributions are narrow and high as most of the trajectories are still close to the rectilinear crack path. As the distance from the notch tip increases, the distributions become wider indicating a lower probability of finding a trajectory in any one place, but the range over which they exist is larger. Such behavior is an important feature of diffusion type processes. Thus, the set of trajectories pictured in Fig. 2 are treated as Brownian particle paths.

For Brownian motion, the variance of the particle position $\sigma^2(y)$ increases linearly with time. The coefficient of proportionality corresponds to the diffusion coefficient.

The correspondence between Brownian motion and the crack trajectories in Fig. 2 dictates that an effective distance from the notch tip along the x axis would substitute time in a conventional diffusion process. From dimensional analysis the only invariant parameter of the dimension of length in crack propagation process is

$$\lambda = \frac{E \cdot \langle G \rangle}{\pi \cdot \sigma_{\infty}^2} \quad \text{-----} \quad (2)$$

Figure 5 shows the relationship between variance of the trajectories $\sigma^2(y)$ and the invariant length λ in the form:

$$\sigma^2(y) = D \cdot \lambda \quad \text{-----} \quad (3)$$

Figure 5: Variance of crack trajectory as a function of effective crack length in the form of equation (3).

It is almost perfectly linear as the correlation coefficient from linear regression analysis is 0.998. The coefficient of the proportionality D with dimension of meters ($D = 0.165$ mm in our present study) characterizes deviation of the "diffusive" crack from the "shortest" path is a candidate for a material parameter. The larger D , the more resistive the composite to crack propagation.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Fatigue fracture in short fiber-glass beads polyester composite propagates as a single path crack. Heterogeneity of the structure is manifested in the random features of fracture. These include random crack trajectories and fluctuation of critical length and critical stress.
2. The critical energy release rate G_{1c} being dependent on the crack trajectory, the critical crack length, and the critical stress which are random variables appear as a random quantity as well. G_{1c} ranges from 1 to 12 kJ/m² with an average value of 6.9 and standard deviation of 3.2 kJ/m².
3. A new parameter, i.e., Crack Diffusion Coefficient is introduced to characterize the ability of the material to deviate the crack path from the most dangerous (maximum energy release rate) path.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge financial support of the NASA-Lewis Research Center under contract number NAG3-585-2. We also wish to extend our gratitude to the Premix Corporation for sample preparation.

REFERENCES

1. A. Chudnovsky, "Crack Layer Theory", NASA Contractor Report 174634, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Washington, D.C., March 1984.
2. A. Chudnovsky and A. Moet, "Thermodynamics of Translational Crack Layer", J. Mater. Sci., 1985, 20, 630-635.
3. P.X. Nguyen and A. Moet, "Fatigue Fracture of Short Glass Fiber Reinforced Poly(vinylchloride): A Crack Layer Approach", J. Vinyl Technology, 1985, 7, 140-149.
4. A. Chudnovsky and A. Moet, "A New Approach to Fracture Toughness Characterization of High Performance Composites", Society of Plastics Engineers-ANTEC, 1984, 30, 370-372.
5. P.X. Nguyen, A. Chudnovsky and A. Moet, "Enhanced Fatigue Resistance of Glass Reinforced PVC Composites", Society of Plastics Engineers-ANTEC, 1985, 31, 381-384.

6. P.X. Nguyen and A. Moet, "The Effect of Fiber-Matrix Adhesion on The Fatigue Behavior of Glass Fiber Reinforced PVC", Polymer Composites, in press.
7. M.A. Mull, A. Chudnovsky and A. Moet, "A Statistical Approach to the Fracture Toughness of Composites", Third Japan-U.S. Conference on Composite Materials", Science University of Tokyo, Japan, June 23-25, 1986.